

CULTiVATE

Co-Designing Food Sharing Innovation
for Resilience

D5.2: Library of Citizen Engagement

WP5 Citizen Engagement with Food Sharing and
Resilience

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Term	Definition
Citizen engagement	<i>Citizen engagement refers to activities which foster people's participation, inclusion, and meaningful involvement in addressing issues of shared concern.</i>
Food Sharing	<i>Food sharing involves collective actions around food and food-related items, spaces, skills and knowledge. It can take place between friends, families, neighbours, communities and strangers across the food system from growing, cooking and eating, to surplus food redistribution.</i>
Citizen Engagement Tool	<i>Citizen engagement tools are instruments, mechanisms or actions designed to facilitate participation, inclusion and/or meaningful involvement in an activity of shared concern.</i>
Serious Games	<i>Serious games are games designed for a specific purpose, which often relates to addressing societal challenges. As such, serious games are games that integrate learning and entertainment.</i>
Co-creation	<i>Co-creation refers to a collective design process to inform the objectives and format of a final product, in our case the Library of Citizen Engagement and four serious games.</i>

Table 1 Glossary of key terms

1. Introduction: Library of Citizen Engagement

Aim of the report

The aim of this report is to present the Library of Citizen Engagement (hereafter The Library), an open-access curated collection of tools, games, and stories to be used by food sharing initiatives, policymakers and citizens for establishing, expanding and maintaining inclusive participation in sustainable food sharing. Effective citizen engagement is vital for realizing inclusive, resilient food sharing, and supporting citizen participation in wider food systems transformation. Food sharing initiatives (FSIs) have valuable lessons to share when it comes to engaging marginalized groups, fostering meaningful participation, and creating welcoming community spaces. The Library was created with FSIs in the context of the EU CULTIVATE project to share their knowledge with a wider public through tools, games and stories for citizen engagement.

What is Cultivate?

CULTIVATE is a four-year Innovation Action funded by the EU Horizon Europe (GA No. 101083377) designed to stimulate sustainable urban and peri-urban (UPU) food sharing activities and help transform urban food systems towards more just and sustainable futures. CULTIVATE will co-design a ground-breaking online social innovation support platform – The Food Sharing Compass – in collaboration with food sharing initiatives (FSIs), local authorities, food supply actors, researchers and citizens to: map, track and monitor UPU food sharing landscapes; identify the costs, benefits and impacts of FSIs; help actors navigate governance architectures and ensure appropriate policies and regulations of food sharing; support increased citizen engagement in UPU food sharing; and create a community of practice for FSIs. Working collaboratively with multiple actors, CULTIVATE will develop more sustainable, resilient and healthy UPU food systems supporting inclusive climate mitigation and adaptation ambitions of the EU. The Library was developed as part of WP5: Citizen engagement in food sharing for resilience and it will be a central pillar of the Food Sharing Compass. The platform will make it possible to navigate diverse food sharing landscapes and cultures in order to understand, develop, replicate, expand and strengthen sustainable food sharing in Europe, supporting the European Green Deal's Action Plan, Food 2030, the Farm to Fork Strategy and the EU's climate change ambitions. The Library highlights a diversity of citizen engagement tools that can be adapted to different audiences, aims, and types of food sharing.

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What is food sharing?

Food sharing involves collective actions around food and food related items, spaces, skills, and knowledge. It can take place between friends, families, neighbours, communities, and strangers across the food system from growing, cooking, and eating to surplus food redistribution. In CULTIVATE we focus on food sharing beyond friends and family, and specifically initiatives explicitly set up to share food. We call these food sharing initiatives (FSIs). FSIs adopt different organizational forms, including co-operatives and social enterprises, charities, and for-profits, and can be community, private-sector or state-led. Examples include seed libraries, community gardens, food-related co-operatives, community kitchens, and surplus food redistribution organizations.

Structure of this report

In what follows, we introduce the Library prototype, both the online and offline versions. Secondly, we elaborate on the methodology used to collect data and develop the library, including testing and refining. We then describe the WP5 strategy for the replication of the Library of Citizen Engagement, including the four serious games and the Lab & Kitchen interventions.

2. The Library of Citizen Engagement

The Library of Citizen Engagement is an online and physical catalogue to support individuals and organizations in enhancing citizen's participation in food sharing. It highlights the benefits of collaboration between citizens, community leaders, researchers, artists, and governments, using place-based approaches to address sustainability challenges. The tools featured in the library aim to meet the needs of food sharing initiatives, reducing barriers for participation and promoting inclusive engagement.

This resource is a curated collection of tools, games, and stories that showcase the range of skills, expertise, and practices for driving positive change across diverse projects or organizations.

The Library of Citizen Engagement aims to:

- Provide practical tools for organizations involved in direct action, community service, research, advocacy, governance, and business to expand and deepen engagement in their food sharing efforts.

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- Showcase innovative examples that reflect the social benefits of integrating food sharing into existing citizen engagement strategies
- Highlight the strengths and opportunities of integrating different citizen engagement tools into food sharing and other sustainability efforts.

The library is divided into four sections:

- **Tools:** This section showcases a list of 62 tools for citizen engagement. Each entry includes a brief description, target audience, stakeholders, engagement outcomes, practical tips, and links to additional resources.
- **Games:** This section outlines 21 different games, their audiences, and their intended purposes, to be used in food sharing contexts.
- **Stories:** This section offers a compilation of 15 narrative stories, illustrating how various organizations developed and adapted citizen engagement tools to meet their specific objectives.
- **About:** This section offers more information on how the Library was developed and how to navigate it. The Library of Citizen Engagement (hereafter the Library), exists in interactive digital and physical formats. We designed and tested both versions of the Library simultaneously to learn from each format while enhancing their synergies and accessibility.

The Library is hosted on the web platform Softr and can be publicly accessed here:

<https://LibraryofCitizenEngagement.softr.app>

The database that populates the Library is hosted in AirTable and managed by Wageningen University. It can be viewed here:

<https://airtable.com/appw1vBshYiJoVDtc/shrh7JVvgSjM80jDG>

2.1 Online Library Functionalities & How to Navigate

To explore the online Library of Citizen Engagement, visit this [link](#), which will take you to the homepage. From there, users can click on the relevant sections, such as Tools, Games, Stories, or About, using the buttons on the opening page. Alternatively, they can scroll down for a comprehensive overview of all available entries or use the drop-down menus for targeted browsing.

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Clicking on an individual entry provides full details, including key insights and additional resources on how to implement the specific tools.

The Library offers a search and filter function to enhance usability. In the Tools section, users can enter a keyword in the search bar, apply filters for Tool Format, Tool Purpose, or Target Group, and reset the search by clearing the search bar and deselecting all filters. In the Games section, users can search by entering keywords, filter results by Game Format or Game Purpose, and start a new search by clearing the search bar and removing selected filters. The Stories section allows keyword searches and filtering by Food Sharing Type. In the About section, users can scroll down to find details on methodology, terminology, navigation instructions, collaborators, and funding sources, with the option to click on specific buttons to jump to relevant sections.

To navigate the online Library users can:

1. Click on the buttons on the opening page you will be re-directed to the section (Tools, Games, Stories, About).
2. Scroll down to have a global view of the entries OR use the drop-down menus under the individual sections.
3. To view an individual entry, click on the individual entry icon. In the individual entry scroll down to see all the fields.

Tools (Figure 1)

- Use the search bar by inserting a keyword.
- Use the Tool Format drop-down menu to select a filter.
- Use the Tool Purpose drop-down menu to select a filter.
- Use the Target Group drop-down menu to select a filter.
- To restart the search, clear the search bar and de-select previously selected filters.

Games (Figure 2)

- Use the search bar by inserting a keyword.
- Use the Game Format drop-down menu to select a filter.
- Use the Game Purpose drop-down menu to select a filter.
- To restart the search, clear the search bar and de-select previously selected filters.

Stories (Figure 3)

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- Use the search bar by inserting a keyword
- Use Food Sharing Type drop-down menu to select a filter.

About Section (Figure 4)

- Scroll down to retrieve information on the Methodology and Terminology, Navigation Instructions, Collaborators and Funding.
- Click on the button to be redirected to a specific paragraph.

Figure 1 Library of Citizen Engagement : Tools Section

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Figure 2 Library of Citizen Engagement: Game Section

Figure 3 Library of Citizen Engagement: Stories Section

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2.2 Physical Library

The physical library is a condensed version of the online database consisting of a card deck (Figure 4) featuring the 62 Citizen Engagement Tool entries (Figure 5) and the 21 games in the Game Section inventory (Figure 6). The Story Section has been organized in 15 booklets corresponding to each individual story (Figure 7). Additionally, it contains 4 four booklets with corresponding playbooks and instructions for the print-and-play version of the four serious games developed by Wageningen University for CULTIVATE. The playbooks will allow easy access for printing each of the four serious games in their local language. Twenty copies of the physical library will be initially distributed to CULTIVATE consortium partners for community use, dissemination, and feedback. The physical library will be further tested and adapted in six different local contexts during the replication phase of the project.

Figure 4 Library of Citizen Engagement Physical Deck

Compact version of the library with and in A5 box

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Figure 5 Tool Cards, Library of Citizen Engagement Deck

Figure 6 Game Cards, Library of Citizen Engagement Deck

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Figure 7 Stories Booklet, Library of Citizen Engagement Deck

Figure 8 How-to-Guide Booklet, Library of Citizen Engagement Deck

3. Methodology

The Library was compiled over a period of two years, from March 2023 to March 2025 (Figure 9). Compiling the database of citizen engagement tools required a global approach to the dimensions of citizen engagement and a thorough investigation of what food sharing practitioners find useful for their work. To appeal to different audiences and organizational capacities, the Library includes diverse tools and activities proven to facilitate engagement. The methodology section documents (1) the data collection process ; (2) the development of the Library framework, including sections, field classifications and coding for the curation of entries; (3) lessons learned through testing citizen engagement tools in public-facing workshops; (4) the translation and testing of the online and physical Library formats. A complete timeline of the Library development process is illustrated in Figure 9.

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The data collection phase (T5.1, Milestone 8) explored how social norms and local conditions influence food sharing. Insights from literature reviews, web searches, and interviews with 15 FSIs helped identify engagement strategies, barriers, and enablers. Tools identified were analysed using a SWOT framework and categorized in AirTable. At the end of the data collection phase (Milestone 8), the Library contained 81 entries. The activation phase (T5.2, Milestone 9) tested tools through workshops, game co-design sessions, and Lab & Kitchens, refining categories based on real-world applications. Developed collaboratively with Food Sharing Initiatives, the Library's digital and physical versions evolved in tandem. The refining phase (T5.3) improved the Library's format, content, and functionality incorporating insights from an online Citizen Engagement Library Survey. Designers from Play the City were contracted, after submitting a competitive subcontracting bid, to enhance the Library's visual accessibility. The Library in both online and physical format is ready for replication in Spoke locations (WP6, T6.2.4) and will continue to expand further in the Replication phase. These actions will be supported and informed by the replication roadmap and template developed by ICELI, and Dissemination and Exploitation plans developed by ICONS. The following sections detail each phase of the Library development process.

Library of Citizen Engagement Timeline

Figure 9 Development Library of Citizen Engagement Timeline 2023-2025

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3.1 Library Development: Data Collection & Online Database

Data collection for Task 5.1: *State-of-the-art review of theories and methods for changing social norms and the impact on citizenship engagement* began in March 2023 with a literature review, stakeholder interviews, and desk research. The literature review examined how evolving social norms, practices, and local conditions influence social innovation in urban and peri-urban food sharing. It also played a crucial role in defining key terminology for web searches, identifying food-sharing initiatives, and shaping the Library's design by informing the selection and categorization of tools.

Through stakeholder interviews, we gathered insights on citizen engagement tools and activities used by FSIs, governments, and civil society groups to encourage participation in food sharing. Both the literature review and interviews helped identify barriers and enablers of citizen engagement, as well as existing tools used to foster involvement. A SWOT analysis further assessed the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with different engagement strategies. To expand the list of citizen engagement tools, we applied a snowball sampling identifying FSIs through recommendations and further reviewing digital sources such as initiative websites, reports, and global databases (e.g., SHARECITY 100). FSIs ICT pages were screened for citizen engagement strategies either looking for mentions of specific activities (dinners, composting) and methodologies used in implementation (workshop outlines, how-to guides, etc). The searches were shaped by the terminology used in food-sharing discourse and our linguistic capabilities, drawing predominantly from sources in English, with some material in Italian, Romanian, Spanish, German, Czech, and Dutch. Consequently, our findings are most reflective of food-sharing practices in Europe and North America. However, we acknowledge that food sharing is a global phenomenon practiced in diverse contexts, which allows for the continuous expansion for the Library to include wider perspectives. The following section provides an in-depth explanation of the data collection process, beginning with the literature review, followed by stakeholder interviews, and detailing the web search strategies used to uncover citizen engagement tools.

3.1.1 Literature Review

The aim of the literature review was to assess how existing research on food-sharing practices provides insights into changing social norms, local conditions, and cultures in urban and peri-urban

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settings. To identify relevant literature, we conducted searches in the SCOPUS database using three distinct queries based on key terms from the three sectors of food sharing: growing, cooking and eating, and surplus redistribution. Additionally, we used Research Rabbit—an AI-driven snowball sampling tool—to expand our search. This process yielded 51 publications relevant for further analysis, with 27 papers focusing on shared growing, 25 on joint cooking and eating, and 22 on surplus food redistribution.

To systematically analyse the literature, we applied both inductive and deductive coding methods using Atlas.ti. For the development of the Library of Citizen Engagement, the literature review was instrumental in identifying concrete examples of how food-sharing practices foster citizen engagement. It provided empirical evidence on the diverse mechanisms used by food-sharing initiatives (FSIs) to involve residents in public life, ranging from one-time workshops, open-day events, and co-creation sessions to long-term commitments such as ambassador programs and volunteering schemes. Beyond identifying engagement strategies, the literature also informed the conceptual framework of the Library. Key insights from the reviewed studies offered preliminary input into the terminology, categories, and classification criteria used to structure the Library, ensuring it reflects the breadth of citizen engagement tools documented in food-sharing research. Table 3, Section 3.1.4 presents the categorization developed based on these findings.

3.1.2 Interviews

To validate and expand upon the literature review findings, we conducted fifteen interviews—twelve with consortium partners from the CULTIVATE project and three with independent practitioners based in Utrecht, the Netherlands. These interviews explored various aspects of citizen engagement across three food-sharing sectors: growing, cooking and eating, and surplus redistribution. Topics included engagement opportunities, challenges, outreach strategies, and inclusion practices. Additionally, interviewees provided insights into the evolving role of FSIs, particularly in response to external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

The interviews yielded concrete examples of citizen engagement activities and tools used by FSIs. Engagement formats varied widely, from highly interactive, resource-intensive activities—such as daily or weekly community meals (e.g., Taste Before You Waste, Zusammen Leben) and garden

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action days (Zusammen Leben)—to more targeted, thematic events designed for specific groups, such as cooking workshops (Nesehnuti, Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, UpFarming), Lab & Kitchen events (Cascoland), and farm tours (The Outsiders). These activities differ in participant commitment levels and resource requirements on the side of the organizers. For example, Brighton & Hove Food Partnership’s cooking workshops require no prior experience but are tailored to specific participant needs, such as supporting individuals with mental health conditions or providing budget-conscious meal planning for those distanced from the labour market. In contrast, Cascoland’s Lab & Kitchen events are curated to bring together diverse stakeholders to address targeted issues, such as neighbourhood development planning.

Crucially, the interviews highlighted how different citizen engagement tools require distinct resources, logistical considerations, and facilitation approaches. For instance, gleaning and market surplus collection efforts, depend on transportation logistics of people and foodstuffs, while large-scale community meals require access to professional kitchens and dining spaces. Meanwhile, thematic events, demand more planning and facilitation expertise than recurring activities, which benefit from established routines and a mix of experienced and novice participants. These insights were carefully considered in structuring and categorizing the Library sections by expanding the range of engagement tools and refining their classification based on participant involvement, resource needs, and intensity. Table 2 in Section 3.1.2 provides an overview of the FSIs and the citizen engagement tools used, illustrating how these findings contributed to the Library’s development.

Type of Food Sharing	Citizen Engagement Tools	FSIs interviewed
Growing	Garden action days <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planting, Pruning, Weeding, Infrastructure building, etc. - Skill sharing events 	Zusammen Leben; Cascoland; Brighton and Hove Food Partnership

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	<p>Collective plots/ growing infrastructure such as green houses, vertical farming plots, communal composting schemes, tool sharing</p>	<p>Zusammen Leben; UpFarming-Brighton and Hove Food Partnership</p>
	<p>Individual garden plots</p>	<p>Zusammen Leben</p>
<p>Cooking and eating</p>	<p>Thematic events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cooking workshops for diverse audiences (elderly; people suffering from dementia; people recovering from addiction; neurodivergent people) - cultural evenings led by migrant communities 	<p>Brighton and Hove Food Partnership; Nesehnuti</p>
	<p>Cook-ins</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pop-up dinners at various locations - caterings for solidarity events - public cooking demonstrations using mobile infrastructures 	<p>Cascoland; TasteBeforeYouWaste; BasicActivistKitchen</p>
	<p>Daily/Weekly meals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - wasteless dinners 	<p>ZusammenLeben; TasteBeforeYouWaste</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - solidarity cafes with sliding scale payments - Climate Kitchen 	
	<p>Street actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Picnics - Festivals - Public art performances - Food forums 	<p>Dublin City Council; Utrecht Municipality; Milan Municipality & Foodwave; Pla Estategic Metropolitana de Barcelona (PEMB);</p>
Surplus Food Redistribution	<p>Free shops/ markets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wasteless markets - Community fridge - Give-away shelves 	<p>TasteBeforeYouWaste; Basic Activist Kitchen; CASCOLAND</p>
	<p>Awareness campaigns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School programs - Cineforums 	<p>Espigoladors – ‘Comida no se tira’ Campaign</p>
	<p>Gleaning marathons</p>	<p>Espigoladors</p>
	<p>Food rescue schemes</p>	<p>Boroume; FoodCloud; TasteBeforeYouWaste</p>
Multifunctional	<p>Guided Tours</p>	<p>The Outsiders – The travelling farm museum of forgotten skills</p>
	<p>Consultation & Focus Groups</p>	<p>Pla Estategic Metropolitana de Barcelona– Agropolis;</p>

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		Comune di Milano- Food Councils; Brighton and Hove Food Partnership
	Infrastructure provision <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community kitchens - Market spaces 	Brighton and Hove Food Partnership; Pla Estategic Metropolitana de Barcelona
	Participatory Budgeting	Brighton and Hove Food Partnership

Table 2 Interviews with FSIs

3.1.3 Desk research

The majority of tools in the Library were identified through desk research, using a combination of targeted web searches, snowball sampling, and iterative database exploration. We conducted searches in global and local databases such as SHARECITY100, Buurtnatuur230, and Karte von Morgen, Interreg Good Practices Map, focusing on food-sharing initiatives and their engagement strategies. We based our initial searches on recommendations gathered from stakeholder interviews as well as the Wageningen’s team experiences with food sharing in Central and eastern Europe, Netherlands, Germany and North America. Based on the literature and interviews we identified flagship actions such as gleaning, food waste collection and processing activities, food campaigns from which we distilled citizen engagement tools.

To ensure a systematic approach, we used key search terms derived from the literature review, including "community kitchens", "thematic dinners", "community engagement toolkits", "diversity and inclusion AND food initiatives", "food games" "food waste actions" and "how-to guide food swap/seed bank". These terms guided our exploration of FSI websites, blogs, newsletters, project reports, and online repositories. Searches were conducted in multiple languages (English, Italian, Romanian, Czech, Spanish, German, Dutch) to capture diverse practices.

3.1.4 First Library Framework

The first iteration of the online Library of Citizen Engagement was completed in September 2023 as part of the *WP5 Task 5.1: State-of-the-art review of theories and methods for changing social norms*

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and the impact on citizenship engagement. The Library database prototype featured 81 entries collected through literature review, interviews and desk research. A codebook resembling Table 3 was assembled to organize information that supports FSIs to make informed decisions about which engagement tools are useful and why. Part of the coding categories used to organize the Library are descriptive and were compiled with information available on the FSIs websites and annual reports, for example, Audience (modified to Target Group), Purpose and Format. To evaluate each entry we applied the SWOT method to each citizen engagement tool and condensed the result into the Pros and Cons fields. The first iteration included additional fields such as Creator, Reflective Questions, Number of Participants, and Logistics, after testing the Library, in the second iteration (T5.2), based on user feedback we decided to replace the fields that proved redundant or remove them altogether due to insufficient information.

The table below (Table 3) documents the terminology created for the classification of tools, games and stories. The three columns explain the field name, description and content. The field content is diverse in terms of format, including text, codes, sliding scale format, illustrations and documents. The fields help users make an informed decision in choosing citizen engagement instruments for their needs. The information presented in Table 3 is embedded in the online database and helps the user navigate the library intuitively.

Tool Section

Field Name	Field Description	Field Content
Description	A brief description of the citizen engagement tool	Text
Tool Format	The structure or medium through which citizen engagement is facilitated, the frame of the specific tool	Art Installation; Award; Event; Governmental Program; Guided Tour; How-to-guide; ICT Tool; Infrastructure; Knowledge Platform; Methodology; Network; Street Action; Toolkit; Training; Workshop;
Tool Purpose	The specific goal or objective of the engagement tool or activity	Awareness raising; Celebration; Community Building; Community Consultation; Skill Building; Skill

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		Sharing; Social Inclusion; Team Building
Target Group	The specific population or demographic that the engagement initiative is designed for; primary audience or beneficiaries of the citizen engagement process	Artists; Chefs; Children; Community Organizers; Elderly; Farmers; General Public; Internal Organization; Neurodivergent people; People with distance from the labor market; People with low literacy; People with migration background; Policy-makers; Researchers; Youth
Participant Engagement	The level of engagement required on the side of the Target Group	High; Medium; Low
Resource Requirements	The tangible and intangible resources needed to implement the tool	Facilitators; Funding; Knowledge; Machinery; Materials; Space; Technology; Time; Transport
Resource Intensity	The level of resources needed to implement and sustain the engagement initiative	5 star rating – from 1 star low intensity to 5 stars high intensity-rated based on the aggregated resource requirements plus financial consideration. ¹
Collaborators	Groups or individuals that act as partners, enablers or co-creators of the engagement process.	Artists; Chefs; Citizens; Community Organizers; Farmers; Policy-makers; Researchers; Youth
Pros	Strengths and opportunities related to implementing the tool.	Text
Cons	Weaknesses and threats associated with the tool	Text
Additional Links	Additional examples from external sources that feature the tool	Link
Supporting Documents	Additional materials supporting the replication of the tool, in PDF format	PDF
Gallery	Custom illustration suggestive of the tool	PNG

¹ It takes into account the fact that some resources can be substituted for others (eg. lack of funding might mean there is more (unpaid) time required and that organizers rely on their personal and professional networks to substitute the lack of a resource (eg funding) with the needed resources for implementation (space, knowledge).

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Game section		
Description	A brief description of the game	Text
Creators	The author or company that distributes the game	Text
Link	Link to the main page of the game	Hyperlink
Purpose	The specific goal or objective of the game as identified by the creators	Awareness Raising; Celebration; Community Building; Community Consultation; Idea generation & Design; Problem Framing; Reflection; Skill Building; Team Building
Target Audience & Age Group	The specific population or demographic that the game is designed for; primary audience of the game as specified by game creators	Age 6-10; Age 10+; Age 12+;
Time Commitment	Time, in hours, allocated for playing the game	Number; To Be Decided ²
Number of Players	The number of players that the game has been designed for	Number; To Be Decided ²
Language	Languages in which the games are available	A list of 52 languages ³
Game Format	The physical or digital format of the game	Board Game; Card Deck; Live Action Role Play; Role-Playing Game; Video Game
Open Access	The accessibility of the game. If the game is open access, the print-and-play version will be found in the Supporting Documents files	Yes/No
Supporting Documents	Additional materials that support the replication of the game, usually the print-and-play versions in PDF format	PDF
Gallery	Illustrations representative of the game	PNG
Story Section		

² Not all games have a strict time or participant number allocation

³ Not all games are available in several languages

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Title	Suggestive title of the story	
Organizer	The name of the FSI featured in the story	Text
Link	Link to the main page of the organization	Hyperlink
Food Sharing Type	Type of food-sharing activities the organization is running	Cooking & eating; Growing; Surplus food redistribution;
Description	A piece of narrative text that describes the organization's origin story and citizen engagement tools they use in their work.	Text
Featured Citizen Engagement Tools	Specific reference to the Library Tool entries featured in the story	62 terms based on the Tool entries
CULTIVATE Webinar	Link to individual webinars created in the context of CULTIVATE featuring food sharing initiatives discussing certain topics of interest for food sharing	Hyperlink
Gallery	A suggestive image that fits the narrative	PNG
About Section		
Library of Citizen Engagement	General description of the library	Text
Terminology	Definition of field categories and codes as presented in this table	Text
How -to-Navigate	Instructions on how to navigate the library	Text
Get in Touch	Contact information of the Library administrators	Text
Acknowledgments	Acknowledgments of people who contributed to the Library development	Text
Funding	Funding information	Text

Table 3 Terminology developed for the Library of Citizen Engagement

The Library database is hosted in AirTable, a cloud collaboration service that uses a spreadsheet-database hybrid to allow different parties to work simultaneously on a project. We chose AirTable for ease of use and maintenance and the appealing visual format.

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3.2 T5.2 Library Development: Testing Citizen Engagement Tools & the Library

The testing of citizen engagement tools and the co-creation of the four serious games took place between September 2023 and September 2024 as part of T5.2. We focused on (1) Enriching the content of the Library by testing twenty citizen engagement tools and developing four serious games, gathering and analysing feedback from the end-users of the tools. (2) Establishing the physical format of the Library by creating the Library Card Deck and testing it in three public facing sessions, gathering input for the physical library prototype in terms of format and content. (3) Improving the functionality of the online database by transferring lessons learned from testing individual citizen engagement tools in the Library Card Deck to the online format.

Table 4 documents the timeline of the testing activities, including an estimation of the number of people involved and the respective citizen engagement tools tested. As detailed in Table 4, Section 3.2.3, key milestones in Library development included iterative testing of citizen engagement mechanisms and refining the four CULTIVATE games, ensuring their adaptability to multiple contexts and participant needs. During two one-month-long Lab & Kitchen events (September 2023 & September 2024), we tested over fifteen citizen engagement tools with approximately 200 residents. Overall, we facilitated thirteen events, tested twenty citizen engagement mechanisms, and engaged approximately 350 people.

Date	Session Title	Event & Venue	Participants	Citizen Engagement Tools
June 2023 [M6]	Cultivating Metaphors for Citizen Engagement	Food Autonomy Festival, Buurtcentrum Rosa, Utrecht	Food Activists & researchers (10 pp)	Metaphors Card Game; CULTIVATE Food Sharing Dictionary Deck
June 2023 [M6]	Library of Citizen Engagement Hackathon	Wageningen University	Internal team (5 pp)	Participatory Mapping; Online Library of Citizen Engagement
September 2023 [M9]	Lab & Kitchen	Rijnvliet, Utrecht	Rijnvliet residents, municipal actors,	Community Cookbooks; Cooking workshops; Outdoor

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			researchers, artists (100 pp)	kitchen infrastructure; Community Food sharing cabinets; Mapping Tools; Public Feasts
September 2023 [M9]	'Oma komt eran' Game Test	Rijnvliet Neighborhood Day, Rijnvliet, Utrecht	Children, Neighbours	'Oma komt eran' Game
October 2023 [M10]	CULTIVATE Zine	Online	Consortium Partners (30 pp) FSIs, Municipal actors, Researchers, Artists	Zine Making; Mail- art
January 2024 [M13]	'Let's Eat' Game Test	Rijnvliet, Utrecht	Neighbours, FSI, Researchers	Let's Eat Game
March 2024 [M15]	'Let's Eat' Game Test	Rural Sociology Research Day, Wageningen	Researchers (30 pp)	Let's Eat Game
April 2024 [M16]	Cultivating a Library for Citizen Engagement	Reinventing the City Conference, AMS Institute, Amsterdam	Researchers	Citizen Engagement Card Deck and Scenarios
May 2024 [M17]	Future of Food Sharing Game Co- creation	CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht	FSIs, Researchers, Policy-makers, Communication Specialists (50 pp)	Citizen Engagement Card Deck, Food Sharing Dictionary Concept Deck
June 2024 [M18]	Cultivating Citizen Engagement in Food Sharing	Thuis, Wageningen	FSIs & Researchers (10)	Beautiful Trouble Card Deck; Citizen Engagement Card Deck
September 2024 [M20]	Lab & Kitchen	Rijnvliet, Utrecht	Food forest stakeholders and Rijnvliet residents, municipal actors, researchers, artists (100 pp)	Cooking Workshops; Mobile Kitchen; Community Potlucks; Participatory Mapping; Community

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				Cookbooks; Swap & Share market
November 2024 [M22]	Library of Citizen Engagement Survey	Online	FSIs, municipal actors, researchers (13 pp)	Online Library of Citizen Engagement
December [M23]	Library Hackathon	Wageningen University	Researchers	Hackathons

Table 4 Testing Citizen Engagement Tools and Library Prototypes

3.2.1 Testing Citizen Engagement Tools and Game Co-creation workshops

Testing citizen engagement tools allowed us to refine and enhance the Library's content while prioritizing accessibility, adaptability, and ease of implementation. As we were concerned with the validity of the findings in a real-world setting, we shaped our testing approach based on calls for contributions to existing events as the Food Autonomy Festival. Equally important as a testing ground was the Lab&Kitchen, which provided us with a public setting and which helped identify community needs, interests, and levels of enthusiasm. This strategic approach ensured that tools were not only effective but also aligned with real-world constraints and opportunities. We emphasized low-tech and low-material approaches to ensure that tools could be applied across diverse community settings with minimal resources. The selection, development, and testing of engagement tools were guided by a SWOT analysis and insights gained from the literature review and the interviews with FSIs. By designing flexible formats, we enabled varying levels of engagement intensity, making the tools adaptable to different contexts. Additionally, public testing settings underscored the importance of usability and real-world applicability, shaping the final structure of the Library and ensuring its relevance for future users.

Through hands-on workshops and public interventions, we tested various tools that shaped the Library's content. At the Food Autonomy Festival in Utrecht, we utilized the New Metaphors Game and Food Sharing Dictionary Card Deck to facilitate collective visioning exercises. These low-material, easily replicable tools proved effective in sparking discussion and informing future game-based facilitation strategies. The success of these formats underscored the need for structured yet adaptable engagement tools, inspiring the development of the game Future Food Sharing and solidifying the Food Sharing Dictionary's role as a reference tool in subsequent co-creation sessions.

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The Lab & Kitchen events in Rijnvliet demonstrated the value of community-based food-sharing initiatives, employing pop-up kitchens, collaborative cooking workshops, and a dynamic cookbook format. The challenges of working in outdoor spaces—such as limited access to water and electricity—highlighted the importance of designing engagement tools that can function in resource-constrained environments. This insight directly influenced how tools in the Library now incorporate adaptability, enablers, and constraints across various settings. The Rijnvliet Community Cookbook, structured for ongoing contributions, became a model for dynamic knowledge-sharing within the Library, informing our approach to continuously evolving content. Insights from these experiences have been integrated into the Pros & Cons fields of individual entries and supplemented with supporting templates. For instance, a How-to-Guide on organizing a Lab & Kitchen has been included in the corresponding entry, and the Rijnvliet Cookbook now features under the Community Cookbooks section of the Library.

Field interventions also allowed us to refine twenty citizen engagement entries and finalize two games: Oma Komt Eran and the Let's Eat Game. The practical testing process provided valuable documentation for the Story Section, capturing both the Lab & Kitchen methodology and the game co-design experience. These insights ensure that FSIs partners and other stakeholders can replicate and implement these tools effectively in their own contexts. For the online and physical development of the library, these interactions led to the careful curation of Library entries, the creation of meta-level codes, and a refined categorization system (Table 2, Section 1.1.2). The parallel development of the physical and online Library versions prioritized accessibility, ensuring that both formats remained user-friendly and widely applicable.

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Figure 10 Lab & Kitchen, September 2023, Utrecht

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Figure 11 Let's Eat Game Launch, Lab & Kitchen, September 2024, Utrecht

3.2.2 Testing and Improving the Library of Citizen Engagement

Through our testing of the Library, we identified several key insights that shaped the development of both the physical and online versions. Inspired by the success of the use of the New Metaphor cards for the collective visioning session at the Food Autonomy Festival (June 2023), we decided to condense the Library online content into a Library of Citizen Engagement Card Deck. This decision was driven by observations that the structured prompts in card decks help participants grasp abstract concepts, encourage creativity, and make unexpected connections. The versatility of this format allowed for easy adaptation to different topics and audiences, reinforcing its value as a citizen engagement tool. Additionally, their portability and low-tech nature makes them accessible in diverse settings, from workshops and public meetings to informal gatherings. Furthermore, we tested the Library deck in three key sessions:

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1. **Reinventing the City Conference (April 2024):** We introduced a scenario-based game using Scenario Cards developed from interviews with FSIs and CULTIVATE Webinars. This process led to the creation of a detailed case library contextualizing food sharing initiatives, which was later integrated into the Library's Story section.
2. **CULTIVATE General Assembly (May 2024):** A co-creation session with CULTIVATE partners focused on gathering input and feedback on the cards while exploring additional game dynamics beyond the Library deck. The session confirmed the versatility of the card format in stimulating discussion and creative problem-solving. It also laid the groundwork for **Game 4: Future Food Sharing**.
3. **Workshop on Citizen Engagement (June 2024):** This session incorporated the Beautiful Trouble deck into testing, introducing new ways to frame engagement strategies by emphasizing storytelling and humour. The feedback provided by the participants helped us refine the card layout, re-define essential field categories, and enhance visual appeal (Figure 12). Inspired by this process, we implemented three meta-level codes—Tools, Games, and Stories—which now structure both the online and physical Library.

Since 2023, the CULTIVATE EU project has generated several key outputs that are integrated into the Library of Citizen Engagement as standalone entries or as supporting materials for existing entries:

- **Serious Games [D5.1]:** Wageningen University developed four serious games to engage citizens in different aspects of food sharing, addressing themes such as cooking and eating together, growing food collectively, and redistributing surplus food. Print-and-play versions of these games are available in the Game Section, with Game 4: Future of Food Sharing incorporating Library cards as a game element (Figure 11).
- **Lab & Kitchen How-to Guide [T5.2]:** This guide presents a step-by-step approach to fostering engagement in food sharing through art-based tools developed and tested by CASCOLAND within the Lab & Kitchen intervention in Rijnvliet, Utrecht. The Lab & Kitchen method was adapted within CULTIVATE to facilitate citizen engagement in the Rijnvliet edible neighbourhood. The How-to Guide is featured under the Lab & Kitchen entry in the Tool

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Section, aiming to inspire community organizers interested in creative, participatory methods for food-sharing activities (Figure 10, 11).

- **Food Sharing Dictionary [D2.1]:** This multilingual tool improves awareness and understanding of food-sharing language across urban and peri-urban (UPU) areas. As part of WP5, we used dictionary terms to develop the Food Sharing Dictionary Card Deck, supporting the Future Food Visioning session at the Food Autonomy Festival (2023) and a game co-creation session at the CULTIVATE General Assembly (2024). The deck is available as a standalone product in the Game Section, with a print-and-play version attached.
- **ICLEI Webinars & Buddy Program [T6.1]:** To establish a European Community of Practice (CoP), ICLEI organized monthly webinars (March 2023–March 2024) where CULTIVATE’s 11 FSI partners shared their experiences, including successes, failures, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges. Based on the webinars, FSIs selected buddy partners for reciprocal visits. The Buddy Program is featured under the Buddy System entry in the Tool Section, while the ICLEI webinars are embedded as links in the Story Section under individual FSI entries.
- **Community of Practice Handbook [T6.1]:** Developed through collaboration between the Pla Estratègic Metropolità de Barcelona and Kaos Pilots (KP), this handbook serves as a toolbox for establishing and sustaining a Community of Practice in the future of food-sharing initiatives. It offers methodologies and resources for CoP development and is featured under the Community Engagement Toolkits in the Tools Section.

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Figure 12 Testing the Library of Citizen Engagement Cards, June 2024, Wageningen

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3.3 T5.3 Library of Citizen Engagement: Refining the Online and the Physical Library

From September 2024 to March 2025, we focused on integrating feedback into both the online and physical versions of the Library while refining the four serious games. To enhance accessibility and optimize searches, we transitioned the Library's content from AirTable to the Softr app program, allowing users to access the Library without needing a user account. The Library of Citizen Engagement app is also optimized for mobile use, offering interactive functions.

To further refine the online Library, we launched the Citizen Engagement Library Survey from 19th November to 12th December 2024. We shared the survey through the CULTIVATE website and social media channel as well as the Rural Sociology website and pages at Wageningen University. We received 12 responses. Feedback from respondents led to improvements in accessibility, field categorization, and search functionalities. Respondents requested clearer tool descriptions, enhanced filtering options, and more concrete examples of game applications. These insights guided refinements in the Tool Section, leading to the removal of redundant field categories. In January and February, the Wageningen team ran two internal hackathons to ensure entries are complete and well-documented. Additionally, Play the City designers were subcontracted to create custom-made illustrations for the online tool entries.

In parallel, we refined the physical Library together with Play the City designers, exploring card designs for individual Tool and Game entries to be featured in the physical Library and the Future of Food Sharing Game. Additionally, we transferred the story section in booklet formats, which will be printed and included in the Physical Library. Each CULTIVATE game will be featured in the Library, providing a playbook in English and print-and-play instructions for local languages within the CULTIVATE consortium. The physical Library will be contained in a box organized in the form of an archive. The first iteration of the physical Library will be distributed at the General Assembly in Barcelona (April 2025), where Food Sharing Initiatives will be invited to test it and provide final feedback.

Through these developments, the Library of Citizen Engagement has evolved into a dynamic and interactive repository, synthesizing lessons from co-creation workshops, citizen engagement trials, and gamified facilitation methods. To ensure effective dissemination and application of these

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insights, we integrated the Library Cards into Game 4: Future Food Sharing. The Library has evolved into an interactive repository that synthesizes lessons from co-creation workshops, citizen engagement trials, and gamified facilitation methods. This ensures its flexibility as a continuously evolving resource that supports food sharing initiatives and broader citizen engagement efforts.

We would like to highlight the limitations of the data collection process and the Library framework. Firstly, the literature sources and web searches were conditioned by the terminology related to food sharing and our linguistic capabilities which have influenced the language and location of our findings, drawing heavily from experiences in Europe and North America. Textual sources were analysed primarily in English, with some Italian, Romanian, Spanish, German, Czech, and Dutch. However, we would like to emphasize that food sharing is practised in a much more diverse geography. Furthermore, the Library is not an exhaustive list of engagement tools and we intend to continue its expansion in the Replication phase and beyond the project timeline by accepting feedback and submissions at cultivate.rso@wur.nl.

4. Replication and Dissemination Strategy

Timeline: M29-M41 (May 2025- May 2026)

Partners: UTR, WU, CAS, ICLEI, ICONS, FC, BHFP, UF, NES, ZLEV, BOR, DCC

Actions: The Library of Citizen Engagement (D5.2) will be replicated across six Spoke locations in collaboration with CULTIVATE's FSI partners, to test and validate the mechanisms adapted and co-designed in WP5 (T5.2) to ensure their adaptability to different local contexts. Findings from replication activities will be used to refine the Library of Citizen Engagement to TRL 8, for integration into the Food Sharing Compass (T6.3). The spoke cities replicating and testing the Lab & Kitchen with CASCOLAND and WUR are Lisbon, Freiburg and Athens. The other spoke cities (Dublin, Brno, Brighton) will be testing citizen engagement tools from the Library in consultation with Wageningen University. Online webinars and workshops introducing the Library and each of the CULTIVATE serious games will be facilitated for spoke cities and be accessible to the general public via CULTIVATE YouTube channels.

Key resources: Lab & Kitchen Methodology, Serious Games, Library of Citizen Engagement

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Library of citizen engagement Start: 1-Apr-2025 End: 30-May-2026	WUR	T6.2.4: Replicating library of citizen engagement in spoke locations; 6 workshops with spoke partners on how to do a citizen engagement activity; Provide support while the event is being created (3PM); Refinement and improvements to the engagement mechanisms (3PM).
	CASCOLAND	T6.2.4: Replicating citizen engagement mechanisms through 3 Lab & Kitchen interventions
	DCC	T 6.2.4 Deliver a citizen engagement mechanism in Dublin
	BRIGHTON	T6.2.4 Testing citizen engagement mechanism in Brighton
	FOOD HUB	
	NESHENUTI	T6.2.4 Testing citizen engagement mechanism in Brno
	UPFARMING	T6.2.4 support Lab and Kitchen in Lisbon
	BOROUME	T6.2.4 support Lab and Kitchen in Athens
ZUSAMMEN LEBEN	T6.2.4 Support Lab and Kitchen in Freiburg	

Table 5 Engagement and Replication Roadmap, D6.1, page 21

After the submission of the WP5 D5.2 Deliverable, the Library enters the replication and dissemination phase, however planning for this phase has already begun. Based on the replication strategy the Library will be updated in terms of framework and content. In the replication phase, we intend to create several support tools:

- (1) a webinar for FSIs guiding them through the Library
- (2) an educational video that will explain how to use the Library to a broad audience
- (3) one-on-one consultation sessions for FSIs to identify citizen engagement tools that can be adapted to their local context aligning with the Replication Roadmap Template developed by ICLEI
- (4) continuous monitoring of the cultivate.rso@wur.nl for new input to the Library

At the same time, the Library enters the Dissemination and Exploitation phase. For the dissemination strategy we intend to:

- connect with the FSIs, Game Designer and other citizen engagement actors who are featured in the library, requesting a review of the entries and asking them to further distribute them in their networks
- (5) contribute to ICLEI webinars
 - (6) Create how-to video for the four CULTIVATE games and the Library (ICONS)
 - (7) reach academic audiences through conference presentations, EIP Agri practice abstracts, academic publications based on the experience gathered from testing the citizen engagement tools and the Lab&Kitchen method

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(8) Use the Library database as a didactical material at Wageningen University

5. Conclusion and takeaway

This deliverable summarises the process and output of WP5 Citizen Engagement in Food Sharing, on Task 5.1 and Task 5.2. The Library of Citizen Engagement will be featured on the CULTIVATE website and be embedded in the Food Sharing Compass. In 2025-2026 the Library of Citizen Engagement – including its tools, serious games, and Lab & Kitchen method will be replicated and adapted in CULTIVATE’s three Spokes locations: Freiburg, Lisbon and Athens. In parallel with the on-site replication efforts, online replication strategies will be developed and trialled with three other spoke locations: Dublin, Brno and Brighton. Based on the online and physical experiences, individual Library entries will be updated accordingly. The Library will be updated on an annual basis, and we welcome your suggestions at cultivate.rso@wur.nl.

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